

Autonomous Vehicles in last mile delivery: sustainable approaches in urban area

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Abstract: Innovative technologies are leading the coming revolution in last mile delivery. More efficiency and sustainable approaches are the objectives of the future urban logistics. Autonomous unmanned aerial vehicles delivery and autonomous delivery robots are solutions to reduce and solve issues of transport activities in the cities. The use of different autonomous vehicles in last mile delivery helps supply chain management processes through a different and more reliable logistics approaches. In fact, logistics activities are being challenged today by the rise of e-commerce, especially in urban areas where high deliveries and tight deadlines are required in a congested environment with increasing constraints from authorities. Autonomous vehicles can, used with innovative logistics models, increase the efficiency and sustainability of last-mile delivery activities, reduce impacts to citizens and the environment, and collaborate with other vehicles and road infrastructure to exchange useful data. However, there is still little evidence on the use of these approaches that can support immediate change. This study aims to analyze, through a sequential method, how urban logistics efficiency can be improved with the use of autonomous vehicles and how these may affect economic, environmental, and social impacts. Results obtained through simulations and mathematical models were tested in a case study to verify the effectiveness.

Keywords: Last Mile Delivery, Autonomous Vehicles, Sustainable Logistics, Autonomous Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, Autonomous Delivery Robot

1. Introduction

Last-mile delivery is one of the most complex challenges in modern logistics. The rapid growth of e-commerce and the development of activities purely in urbanized areas is requiring greater technical and technological efforts, to improve economic but also environmental and social performance. More efficiency and sustainable approaches are the objectives of the future urban logistics.

In last-mile delivery the transport means and the logistics model affect the externalities generated by urban transport, such as air emissions, congestion, accidents, climate change, land use, and infrastructure wear. The main logistics model is based on a place (warehouse, hub, etc.) near or within the city where goods arrive, are re-assembled and loaded onto transport vehicles for delivery. Vans and motorcycles are the traditional approach used in this activity. However, vehicles with less impact (in terms of transport externalities) are needed to achieve sustainable objectives. Therefore, different types of vehicles are adopted to fit to urban constraints: the use of electric vehicles instead of ICE vehicles reduces air pollution; electric light vehicles, bike and cargo bike are a useful approach to reduce congestion and urban impacts in high-

density and pedestrian areas, as analysed by Antonakopoulou et al. (2020). In the recent years, new technologies are bringing out small, autonomous, and city-friendly vehicles. The autonomous delivery robots (ADRs) and autonomous unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), also known as autonomous drones, are delivery vehicles suitable in this vision. The advantage of UAVs is speed and traveling the minimum aerial distance between two locations (Euclidian distance), but the limitation is low load capacity. ADRs are ground vehicles which opens new opportunities for optimizing last-mile operations in the cities by reducing issues of transport activities, according to Shuaibu et al. (2025).

It is also necessary to rethink the logistics model by understanding the new needs of cities: traffic congestion, air pollutions, delivery time consumption are significant impacts for citizens and delivery companies. In this context, innovative logistics models with urban and micro-hubs, integrated with ADRs and UAVs, require detailed studies on mathematical modelling. Several studies have proposed optimization schemes to improve delivery efficiency. A simulation-based model to minimize delivery time in drone fleets is proposed by Swanson (2019). Travel distance minimization using ADRs is analysed by Fanti et

al. (2020). A reinforcement learning model for truck-drone coordination is introduced by Bi et al. (2023). A system-level model for robot-supported last-mile delivery is developed by Simoni et al. (2020). The collaborative approach is a promising strategy for the goods relocation problem studied by Silvestri et al. (2021) and for synchronized drones, trucks, and ground robots' operations analysed by Gerrits and Schuur (2021). Optimization of the control and traffic model in the urban area is addressed by Fanti et al. (2014) and a vehicle routing model for coordinated truck-robot systems is formulated by Ostermeier et al. (2022).

By analysing the economic, environmental and social sustainability aspects in the use of ADRs and UAVs in urban areas, interesting approaches and indicators have emerged to compare different last mile logistics strategies. An economic and environmental assessment of truck-drone hybrid systems, in which the main sustainability trade-offs were highlighted, are carried out by Baldisseri et al. (2022). Energy consumption and environmental impact are also important factors. The energy requirements of a mixed fleet of electric vehicles serving parcel delivery activities are analysed by Kirschstein (2021). Operational performance, infrastructure needs, regulatory requirements, and social acceptance as key challenges identified by Alverhed et al. (2024).

ADRs and autonomous UAVs are attractive strategies for improving last mile delivery efficiency and sustainability. The focus of the study on these vehicles is to understand the degree to which current urban needs in last mile delivery are being met. Unlike other types of vehicles, the characteristics of autonomous vehicles analysed, allow for greater benefits. However, there is still little evidence on the use of these approaches that can support immediate change. Indeed, few studies address the multi-objective problem of optimizing sustainability values and travel time. The research question is to understand what strategies to adopt using different autonomous vehicles.

The load capacity of ADRs increases sustainability values, but in most cases the travel time exceeds the target. Therefore, it is possible to optimise sustainability by combining autonomous UAVs only for time-consuming deliveries in order to achieve the travel time target. This study focusses on this approach and analyses a different last-mile delivery strategy: starting from the optimization of the volumetric efficiency of the parcels that an ADR can carry the optimal route to be taken will be evaluated also considering the integration with UAV to deliver the remaining parcels during the ADR's task, in order to meet the target travel time. Finally, the economic, environmental, and social sustainability that this strategy achieves will be evaluated.

2. Methodology

The proposed last-mile delivery model is based on the use of an ADR combined with an autonomous UAV. The higher load capacity and sustainability values in the use of ADR allow the maximum number of parcels to be delivered through a route minimization approach in the allotted travel time. The remaining parcels (beyond the

available capacity and time of the ADR) are delivered by an autonomous UAV. This methodology simultaneously optimizes delivery time and ensures greater logistical sustainability.

2.1 Container loading problem

The efficiency use of an ADR is related to the use of cargo space, considering the weight constraint. This problem is widely known in the scientific literature and can be implemented using a mixed-integer programming formulation, so with all decision variables that are integers and binary. Considering 3D coordinate system, is possible to allocate box parcels into the cargo space. Length, width, height and weight limit of the cargo space and length, width, height, volume, weight, and density of each box parcel are the parameters considered in the problem. The binary decision variables to solve the optimization problem are the box parcel loaded into the cargo space the position of box parcel considering length, width, and height respectively parallel or not to x-axis, y-axis and z-axis, and if are on the right, left, front, back, top and bottom. The integer decision variables are x-axis, y-axis and z-axis, front-left bottom corner of the box parcel.

The objective function is to optimize the load of the cargo space based on the maximization of volume occupied by the loaded box parcel. Constraints are related to physical aspects, such as dimensions, capacity, and weights, of cargo space and boxes parcel. More details on the description of the formulation adopted is possible to collect in scientific study by Liu et al. (2017).

2.2 Aggregate multi-objective function problem

The problem of loading a container covers several aspects and most of them are related to the minimization of the total cost. The problem set in the previous subsection maximizes the volume occupied within the cargo space but not minimizes the total cost and minimizes the total weight of the container. Indeed, maximizing the volume means less trips, and then less travel cost, but minimizing the weight means less energy cost for each trip.

These reasons lead to an optimization problem in which there are two main opposing objectives: maximizing the occupied volume and minimizing the total weight in the container.

The multi-objective method adopted is the aggregate multi-objective function. This approach is to combine all objectives, using the weighted sum method in the linear

combination of all objective functions. The aggregate multi-objective function is implemented as follow:

$$z(x) = \sum_{k=1}^p \lambda_k z_k(x) \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^p \lambda_k = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\max z(x) = \alpha \cdot \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n vol_i \cdot s_i}{Vol\ Cont} \right) - \beta \cdot \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n mass_i \cdot s_i}{Mass\ lim\ Cont} \right) \quad (3)$$

where:

λ_k are positive weight associated to objective functions

$z_k(x)$ are all the objective functions of the problem

α is a weight that refers to maximizing the volume occupied by parcels in the container as an objective function

β is a weight that refers to the minimization of the weight of parcels in the container as an objective function

vol_i is the parameter of volume occupied by each parcel

s_i is the binary decision variables that refers to whether or not of each parcel is loaded into the container

$mass_i$ is the parameter of weight of each parcel

Vol Cont is the parameter of the maximum volume of the container

Mass lim Cont is the parameter of the weight limit of parcels that can be carried in the container

The optimization problem is properly solved by setting the values of the weights correctly. This task is up to the designer, depending on which objective function is considered most important. A good approach to perform it is to vary the weights, respecting constraint (2), so as to monitor how the optimization behaves. In this case, the objective functions are slightly different from the standard case: there is, in fact, normalization to avoid having imbalances within the objective function that could produce erroneous results. In this way, the objective function becomes dimensionless.

2.3 Evaluation alternatives combining ADR with autonomous UAV

The results of the problem require choosing one of the emerging solutions. The choice must favour the one most balanced between the two proposed objectives. This is because packages that will not be transported will still need to be delivered, and the proposed logistics model involves the use of autonomous UAVs that can normally deliver one package at a time. Using only the autonomous UAV would result in a very high number of deliveries and consequent higher energy consumption. Therefore, the goal of minimizing travel is achieved by using the ADR,

considering the travel time limit, and the autonomous UAV to complete the delivery of the remaining parcels.

It should be noted that the proposed model considers two alternatives: i) the use of ADR alone and, ii) the use of ADR in combination with autonomous UAV. During this step it is necessary to check whether the time required to deliver the remaining packages is less or more than that calculated for delivery by robot. In the first case the chosen alternative is accepted while in the second case it is necessary to assess whether with a different alternative (parcels to be transported by robot) it is possible to decrease the time or not. The evaluation will end when this parameter can no longer be improved. If in the first alternative the travel time is not able to give a solution, based on the available time, then the second alternative is adopted. In this case, the autonomous UAV is used in parallel with ADR to achieve the objective of travel time satisfaction and to optimize sustainability values.

The use of UAV allows reducing the distance by considering the Euclidean distance between the starting point and the delivery point. The starting point (hub) is the same as ADR, and the travel time is the sum of flight time, take-off time and landing time (considering the same altitude for take-off and landing). Importantly, the UAV is not interchangeable with other delivery modes such as bikes or motorbikes.

2.4 Travelling Salesman Problem

Increasing the efficiency of the logistics model can be done by setting the correct route for the ADR to minimize distances and time.

The most effective model in the literature is the travelling salesman problem. Applying this approach will reduce battery consumption and minimizes the overall length travelled.

2.5 Sustainability assessment

The use of an ADR combined with an autonomous UAV is an economic and environmental opportunity due to the increase the vehicle volumetric efficiency and the load space saturation ratio in ADR, keep the same time to perform the task. On this basis, an alternative logistic system for last-mile delivery is proposed to provide a more economic, environmental, and social sustainable approach. ADR route optimization allows to increase the logistic system efficiency and reduce transport externalities: the use of autonomous vehicles, small, electric without internal combustion engine, and using defined routes (e.g. sidewalks, bus lanes, bike lanes, pedestrian areas) generates several benefits for city logistics and traffic systems. ADR do not need parking lots during delivery activities. Congestion is reduced, especially in dense urban areas. Energy consumption is lower than traditional light commercial vehicles, and air emissions and pollution are absent in the city. The ADRs can be used throughout the

day and not in defined time windows, as is done in several cities to reduce congestion.

Economic sustainability is affected by the time of use of autonomous vehicles: the high investment or rental cost of ADRs and UAVs can be amortized in a shorter time with a high number of deliveries. Vehicle costs also include software and route scheduling costs, as well as safety costs related to a service remotely management performed with a tele-operator involved in driving the robots when necessary (unsafety condition). In addition, operative costs such as electrical energy, maintenance, personnel, and others are considered.

The sustainable evaluation of the framework of the conceptual model proposed is based on the follow steps:

- analysis of the environmental impact as emissions factors
- study of the economic aspects in the use of autonomous vehicles
- analysis of the social impact as externalities factors affecting citizens

3. Experimental case study

The proposed last-mile delivery model is applied in an experimental urban area, specifically in the Polytechnic University of Bari (Italy). The area is characterized by nine department where parcels are delivered by a central distribution hub, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Departments in the Polytechnic University of Bari

The experimental case study adopts the following assumptions: a random value of parcels (in this case study is 20) and customers located in the nine departments is considered; the size and weight of parcel is chosen randomly within a set of minimum and maximum values; an ADR with a defined load capacity (cargo space: 58.7 cm x 23.3 cm x 22 cm and weight limit: 21.64 kg) and an autonomous UAV with a capacity of a single parcel per flight are considered. The average flight speed and take-off and landing speed of the UAV are defined. Table 3 shows the Euclidean distance between the hub and the departments, and the travel time from the hub to each department using the UAV (considering take-off, landing and return). The delivery time of UAV is the sum of travel time and service time per customer. The area of Polytechnic University of Bari has no fly restrictions, and the take-off and landing distance considered is 30 meters. In the case of areas with no-fly zones, the approach is more

complex because different distances methods are considered.

The input parameters included are as follows:

- ADR average speed: $v = 8 \text{ km/h}$ (133.33 m/min)
- autonomous UAV average speed: $v = 30 \text{ km/h}$ (500 m/min) and vertical take-off and landing speed: $v = 15 \text{ km/h}$ (250 m/min)
- Service time per client: $t_{\text{serve}} = 0.5$ minutes per parcel
- Maximum parcel dimension: 30 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm
- Minimum parcel dimension: 8 cm x 5 cm x 3 cm
- Maximum parcel weight: 1.2 kg
- Minimum parcel weight: 0.23 kg

Table 1 reports the number of parcels requested by each department.

Table 1: Parcel demand

Department	Parcels required
1	4
2	2
3	3
4	2
5	4
6	1
7	5
8	3
9	6

Table 2 shows the pairwise distances (in meters) between hub and the departments. This matrix is used in the travelling salesman problem to evaluate the shortest route.

Table 2: Matrix of rectangular distance between departments

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0	-	65	74	99	290	350	440	500	740	1000
1	65	-	82	99	130	260	350	600	750	920
2	74	82	-	50	210	300	400	700	800	850
3	99	99	50	-	220	350	450	650	700	750
4	290	130	210	220	-	130	190	450	550	600
5	350	260	300	350	130	-	260	400	500	550
6	440	350	400	450	190	260	-	400	550	600
7	500	600	700	650	450	400	400	-	220	400
8	740	750	800	700	550	500	550	220	-	50
9	1000	920	850	750	600	550	600	400	50	-

Table 3: Euclidean distance in the use of a UAV between hub and departments

Department	Euclidean distance between hub and department [mt.]	Travel time from hub and department and return [sec.]
1	105	39.6
2	130	45.6
3	150	50.4
4	175	56.4
5	220	67.2
6	290	84
7	355	99.6
8	485	130.8
9	655	171.6

3.1 Results of container loading problem

The input data are used to perform four simulations with a variation of the parcel dimension of the same problem. The results are obtained with software AMPL and a 3D visualization is proposed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: 3D visualization of the loaded parcels inside the cargo space

The results of the four simulations are summarized in Table 4. The analysis shows that an average of 85,5% of the total cargo space volume is occupied by parcels.

Table 4: Results of cargo space volume occupied

Simulation	Volume percentage	Mass loaded
1	85.5 %	71.0 %
2	86.4 %	90.4 %
3	83.2 %	93.3 %
4	82.9 %	84.5 %

3.2 Results of aggregate multi-objective function problem

The optimization problem is implemented by CPLEX solver. The value of the weights assigned to alpha and beta are opposite since the objective functions are a maximization and minimization, respectively. Specifically, starting from alpha value of 0.9 and beta of 0.1, in subsequent simulations alpha decreases and beta increases by a value of 0.1. The calculations were set with a stop criterion of one hour from the start of the optimization process. Any small inconsistencies in the results may be related to this constraint. However, results confirm the values obtained in the previous method.

The results are summarised in the Table 5.

Table 5: Results of aggregate multi-objective function problem

α	β	Volume percentage	Mass loaded percentage	Objective function value
0.9	0.1	85.7 %	73.7 %	0.69
0.8	0.2	81.5 %	61.1 %	0.52
0.7	0.3	81.4 %	60.2 %	0.41
0.6	0.4	81.3 %	57.4 %	0.25
0.5	0.5	75.9 %	49.4 %	0.13
0.4	0.6	28.8 %	10.5 %	0.05
0.3	0.7	28.8 %	10.5 %	0.01

Figures 3 and 4 show the trends of the parameters considered in graphical form.

Figure 3: Plot graph of mass and volume trend

Figure 4: Multi-objective function values for different α and β

3.3 Results of alternatives evaluation with autonomous UAV

Based on the results obtained in the multi-objective function problem, it is possible to have 12 parcels delivered with the ADR. The other parcels will be delivered with UAV. Random assignment of parcels to departments produces the condition proposed in Table 6.

Table 6: Number of parcels delivered with ADR and UAV in each department

Department	Parcels delivered with ADR	Parcels delivered with UAV
1	1	1
2	2	0
3	1	1
4	1	1
5	0	2
6	0	2
7	3	0
8	1	1
9	3	0

The total time necessary to delivery eight parcels in the different departments with an autonomous UAV as proposed in Table 6, is equal to 15.09 minutes. Considering this alternative, it is necessary to check that the total time of deliveries made with the autonomous UAV is less than the total time of deliveries made with the ADR, otherwise it will be necessary to check if there is another better alternative. Following the calculation of the best route with the ADR, it is possible to calculate the overall times.

3.4 Results of travelling salesman problem

The travelling salesman problem is implemented by online software (w3schools.com). The best route with the ADR involves delivering parcels to departments, starting from the hub (identified with 0), in this order: 0, 1, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 5, 2, 3, 0. The total distance travelled is equal to 2054 mt.

The total time for this task with ADR is 21.41 minutes. Therefore, it is possible to delivery all package with an ADR and an autonomous UAV in the same overall time.

3.5 Results of sustainability assessment

The assumption of economic aspects is related to an ADR investment cost of 5,000 €, with a depreciation period of 4 years, 220 working days in a year, 18 km in a working day available for delivery, energy cost of 0.30 €/kWh, efficiency factor 30 km/kWh, insurance of 300 €, maintenance 500 €. The autonomous UAV investment cost is equal to 5,500 €, with a depreciation period of 4 years, 220 working days in a year, 24 km in a working day available for delivery (MK-30), energy cost of 0.30 €/kWh, efficiency factor 20 km/kWh, insurance of 300 €, maintenance 500 €. Hourly cost of worker for upload the parcels are not considered.

Implementing data in the case study, a daily cost of the service is about 19.68 € (9.38 € for the ADR and 10.30 € for the autonomous UAV). Most of them are fixed costs, so it is possible to have similar costs (about 21.12 €) if four deliveries are completed in one day.

The environmental impacts for the two autonomous vehicles are linked to air pollutant emissions, considering the electric powertrain used. Externalities considered for this factor are based on the transport external costs proposed in EU Handbook. In each task analysed in the case study, the environmental cost is less than 0.01 €. The analysis considers the emissions resulting from energy consumption, the impact on climate change, and the total distance travelled by each mode of transport.

The social impacts considered for ADR and an autonomous UAV are related to noise pollution and accidents. Externalities considered for these factors are derived by similar vehicles described in the transport external costs proposed in EU Handbook. In each task analysed in the case study, the environmental cost is less than 0.05 €.

3.1 Analysis of results

Optimization is an integer linear problem. Therefore, by increasing the number of parcels and robots, the computational time increase exponentially (NP-hard) and it

is difficult to obtain solution quickly. The model could become scalable by implementing the following method: application of a heuristic that makes an initial breakdown of the parcels for each robot, after which the model will use an optimization on the load capacity in order to assign the parcels specifically to each individual robot. Following this step, a further optimization will focus on each individual robot to obtain the path to be analysed. This approach is distributed and parallelizable, rather than centralized.

4. Conclusion

The proposed last-mile delivery model is based in using an ADR combining with an autonomous UAV. The ADR will be responsible for delivering the maximum number of parcels, based on weight limits, through route minimization. The additional parcels over the capacity of the ADR are delivered with an autonomous UAV to simultaneously optimize delivery time and logistics sustainability.

A simulation case study is used to test this model and analysis the method, the technical results and the sustainability values.

In future work, further analyses will be developed on different scenarios that are closest to new autonomous vehicles and to understand whether which factors most affect the sustainability of the use of these autonomous vehicles in last-mile delivery.

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